

GRAMMATICAL FEATURES OF WRITTEN TRANSLATION: WORKING ON WORD MEANINGS AND WORD COMBINATIONS.

Ubaydullayeva Durдона Rahmonjon qizi

Ferghana State University teacher

Usmonaliyeva Diyoraxon

Sotvoldiyeva Diyoraxon

Sultonova Dildoraxon

Tursunboyeva Shodiyaxon

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Abstract: This article presents comments on grammatical features of written translation: working on word meanings and word combinations.

Key words: comparative grammar, grammatical problems in translation, grammatical root translation, grammatical concordance, pronoun translation, prepositional translation problem.

There is a system of symbols that distinguishes one language from another. Such languages include English and Uzbek. Their grammatical systems differ typologically and genetically. English belongs to the Germanic language group of the Indo-European language family, and Uzbek language belongs to the Turkic language group of the Altaic language family. English has a variable analytic character according to its morphological structure and a synthetic character in terms of writing. The Uzbek language is an agglutinative language.

Қуйидаги мисолларни қиёслаб ўрганиш орқали тиллар ўртасидаги фарқларни кузатиш мумкин:

The hunter killed the wolf. – Овчи бўрини ўлдирди.

I go to school. – Мен мактабга бораман.

From these examples, we can see that sentence structure in Uzbek differs from English. When the word order changes in English, the meaning of the sentence also changes.

In English, the subject-predicate (S-P) word order is expressed in a predicate sentence. In English, the possessor (S) comes at the beginning of the sentence, and the participle (P) comes after the possessor. If the participle is expressed by a transitive verb, the complement comes after the participle: S-P (Vtr)-O.

However, the word order in Uzbek is fundamentally different from the word order in English and can be expressed as follows: S-O-P (Vtr). Comparing the word order in English with the word order in Uzbek, we see that in Uzbek there is an opportunity to change the order of words and the place of the filler.

The hunter killed the wolf.

The wolf was killed by a hunter.

The hunter killed the wolf. (In colloquial speech).

As can be seen from the given examples, the word order is completely different in English and Uzbek languages. In addition to these, in the Uzbek language translation, the suffix -ni adds more clarity to the sentence. Sentences of the English and Uzbek languages can be divided into three types according to their grammatical-morphological and syntactic compatibility:

1. Full adaptation.
2. Partial adaptation.
3. Incompatibility in general.

Complete morphological compatibility is observed when the words have the same meaning in languages with the same grammatical category. In English and Uzbek grammar, the number category is very close to each other.

Partial morphological compatibility occurs when grammatical categories have the same meaning and differ in meaning to a certain extent. This can also be seen in the category of agreement in nouns. In both languages, the meaning of the conjugation is the same, but they differ in terms of their number and the meaning they express. There are two consonants in English and six in Uzbek.

Overall morphological incompatibility. We can observe this situation in the general incompatibility of grammatical categories. For example, in the Uzbek language, the category of possession is expressed through possessive suffixes.

Ўзбек тилида English

Китоб-им my book

Китоб-инг your book

Китоб-и his/her book

The Uzbek possessive category does not correspond to the English possessive category at all. In Uzbek, a possessive suffix is used to express the category of possession, while in English, pronouns are used. In English, we use the definite article to express whether nouns are definite or indefinite. But there is no suitable variant of this grammatical tool in Uzbek. In this case, the meaning of the articles is given using the lexical and syntactic means of the language.

Now let's look at the syntactic compatibility of grammatical compatibility in English and Uzbek languages: Full syntactic compatibility means compatibility of structure, word combinations and parts of sentences. Complete syntactic compatibility between Uzbek and English is rare. We can observe complete syntactic compatibility in the word combination in the form of Adjective + Noun: white flag.

We can see the same situation when the participle of simple sentences is expressed by a transitive verb: He laughed. – У кулди.

In general, syntactic mismatch refers to the lack or mismatch of certain syntactic constructions between the source language and the target language. In English, these syntactic constructions are represented by impersonal forms of the verb that form incomplete or secondary parts of the sentence. The semantic function of predicative constructions means that actions interact with each other and adapt in a specific situation. Although there is no formal grammatical relationship between these constructions and the main clauses of the sentence, there is always agreement between them. In predicative constructions, action or state is defined in the translation of simple and compound sentences. Масалан: I heard the door open. – Эшик очилганини эшитдим.

Types of grammatical transformation. In order to express the information in one language in another language, it is necessary to use several types of lexical and grammatical transformations. Below we consider the types of grammatical transformation, such as grammatical substitution, grammatical transposition, grammatical omission, grammatical addition.

Grammatical substitution is the replacement of one part of a sentence with another part of a sentence or one form of a word with another form of a word. Two situations are observed in grammatical substitution: a) substitution of sentence fragments; b) replacing the grammatical forms of the word.

There are several reasons for transposition translation:

- non-existence of original grammatical forms or constructions in the language being translated;
- lack of consistency in the combination of forms and constructions, as well as the use of different adaptations and words for lexical reasons;
- lack of a sentence with the same meaning.

The following example shows the meaning of the verb by switching the parts of two English sentences:

He says he will come. – У келишини айтяпти.

He said he would come. – У келишини айтди.

Syntactic reconstruction is often required in the translation of inversion sentences, that is, in sentences where words need to be translated in reverse order. Inversion arises from stylistic or spiritual requirements. In English, inversion is a very expressive emphatic device. In grammatical exchange, the original grammatical unit is replaced by another grammatical unit in the target language. This is done through the exchange of word categories (rod, number),

word groups, clauses. For example, in English, a plural noun can appear in a translation with a singular noun or vice versa. For example, money (бирликда) – деньги (кўпликда) – пул (бирликда); struggles (кўпликда) – борьба (бирликда) – кураш (бирликда).

It is worth noting that grammar is a pillar of language. Any alternative to no column or improper construction of the column will also destroy the top-level translation. The study of morphological and syntactic complete alternatives, partial alternatives or incompatibilities in the process of translation through pronouns, articles, grammatical rods, verbs and other grammatical categories clearly shows which way to go in solving problems.

Reference:

1. Чужакин А., Палажченко П. Мир перевода. – Москва: Валент, 1997. – 192 с.
2. Шарипов Ж. Бадий таржималар ва таржима назарияси. – Т., 1972.
3. Швейцер А. Д. К проблеме лингвистического изучения процесса перевода // Вопросы языкознания. 1970. – № 4. – 216 с.
4. Швейцер А. Д. Перевод и лингвистика. – Москва, 1973. – 310 с.
5. Швейцер А. Д. Теория перевода. Статус, проблемы, аспекты. – М.: Наука, 1988. – 364 с.
6. Ғоппорова, Н., & Убайдуллаева, Д. (2022). КОММУНИКАТИВНО-ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ ДИРЕКТИВНЫХ РЕЧЕВЫХ АКТОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(12), 825-827.
7. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА ҚЎШМА ГАПЛАР ТАВСИФИ, ТАСНИФИ ВА МЕТАТИЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. Science and innovation, 1(В6), 560-564.
8. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA IJTIMOİY YO'NALISHNING TARAQQIYOTI. Science and innovation, 1(В6), 869-873.
9. Убайдуллаева, Д. (2022). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ОПИСАНИЯ, КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ И МЕТАТАЛОГИИ СЛОЖНЫХ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЙ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ. Наука и инновации, 1(6), 560-564